

Quarter Symmetric Metric Connection on Generalized Semi Pseudo Ricci Symmetric Manifold

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Abstract: Object of this paper is to find some properties of generalized semi pseudo Ricci symmetric manifold (denoted by $G(SPRS)_n$) admitting quarter symmetric metric connection. At last we have given an example of this manifold.

Key Words: Generalized semi pseudo Ricci symmetric manifold, semi pseudo Ricci symmetric manifold, pseudo Ricci symmetric manifold, quarter symmetric metric connection.

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§1. Introduction

The notion of locally symmetric and Ricci symmetric Riemannian manifold began with work of Cartan [10] and Eisenhart[8] respectively. A Riemannian manifold is said to be locally symmetric if its curvature tensor R satisfies the relation

$$\nabla R = 0, \quad (1)$$

where ∇ is the operator of covariant differentiation w.r.t. the metric tensor g . Again a Ricci symmetric manifold is a Riemannian manifold with the Ricci tensor S of type (0,2) satisfying

$$\nabla S = 0. \quad (2)$$

After them these notions have flowed in several branches such as recurrent manifold, Ricci-recurrent manifold, semi-symmetric manifold, pseudo-symmetric manifold[4], pseudo Ricci-symmetric manifold[6] and so on.

A non flat Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) , $(n > 2)$ is said to be pseudo Ricci symmetric manifold $((PRS)_n)$ [5] if Ricci tensor S is not identically zero and satisfies

$$(\nabla_X S)(Y, Z) = 2A(X)S(Y, Z) + A(Y)S(X, Z) + A(Z)S(X, Y), \quad (3)$$

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where A is nonzero 1-form satisfying

$$g(X, U) = A(X) \quad (4)$$

for a particular vector field U .

A non flat Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) , $(n > 2)$ is said to be semi pseudo Ricci symmetric manifold $((SPRS)_n)$ [2] if Ricci tensor S is not identically zero and satisfies

$$(\nabla_X S)(Y, Z) = A(Y)S(X, Z) + A(Z)S(X, Y), \quad (5)$$

where A is nonzero 1-form satisfying

$$g(X, U) = A(X) \quad (6)$$

for a particular vector field U .

A non flat Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) , $(n > 2)$ is said to be generalised semi pseudo Ricci symmetric manifold $(G(SPRS)_n)$ [1] if Ricci tensor S is not identically zero and satisfies

$$(\nabla_X S)(Y, Z) = A(Y)S(X, Z) + B(Z)S(X, Y) \quad (7)$$

where A, B are nonzero 1-forms satisfying

$$g(X, V) = A(X) \quad (8)$$

$$g(X, W) = B(X) \quad (9)$$

for particular vector fields V, W respectively.

From the above definition we observe that when $\delta = A - B$ is identically zero, $G(SPRS)_n$ reduces $(SPRS)_n$.

Consider a non flat Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) , $(n > 2)$ with a Riemannian connection ∇ . We define a linear connection D on M by

$$D_X Y = \nabla_X Y + H(X, Y), \quad (10)$$

where H is a tensor field of type $(0, 2)$.

Now D is said to be quarter symmetric connection on M if the torsion tensor \bar{T} with respect to D satisfies

$$\bar{T}(X, Y) = \eta(Y)QX - \eta(X)QY, \quad (11)$$

where Q is the symmetric endomorphism of the tangent space at each point of a $G(SPRS)_n$ corresponding to the Ricci tensor S .

D is said to be metric connection if

$$(D_X g)(Y, Z) = 0. \quad (12)$$

The above relations will be used in the followings.

§2. Preliminaries

Let a non flat Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) , $(n > 2)$ which is $G(SPRS)_n$ and Q be the symmetric endomorphism of the tangent space at each point of M corresponding to the Ricci tensor S . Then M satisfies (7) and

$$g(QX, Y) = S(X, Y). \quad (13)$$

Again from (7) we can get

$$(\nabla_X S)(Y, Z) - (\nabla_Y S)(X, Z) = A(Y)S(X, Z) - A(X)S(Y, Z). \quad (14)$$

Contracting above with respect to Y and Z , we have

$$dr(X) = 2\bar{A}(X) - 2A(X)r, \quad (15)$$

where $\bar{A}(X) = A(QX)$.

Now let ∇ be the Riemannian connection and D be a quarter symmetric metric connection on M and \bar{T} is the torsion tensor with respect to D . Then from (10) and (12), we have,

$$g(H(X, Y), Z) + g(H(X, Z), Y) = 0. \quad (16)$$

From (10) and (11) we can obtain,

$$H(X, Y) - H(Y, X) = A(Y)QX - A(X)QY. \quad (17)$$

Then (16) and (17) gives us the following,

$$H(X, Y) = A(Y)QX - S(X, Y)V, \quad (18)$$

where V is a particular vector field such that $g(X, V) = A(X)$. Then (10) can be written as

$$D_X Y = \nabla_X Y + A(Y)QX - S(X, Y)V. \quad (19)$$

§3. Curvature Tensor with Respect to a Quarter Symmetric

Metric Connection on $G(SPRS)_n$

Let R, S, r be the curvature tensor, Ricci tensor, and scalar curvature respectively with respect to Riemannian connection ∇ on M . Again let $\bar{R}, \bar{S}, \bar{r}$ be the curvature tensor, Ricci tensor, and scalar curvature respectively with respect to a quarter symmetric metric connection D on M . Then

$$\bar{R}(X, Y, Z) = D_X D_Y Z - D_Y D_X Z - D_{[X, Y]}Z. \quad (20)$$

Then (14), (19) and (20) gives us,

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{R}(X, Y, Z) = & R(X, Y, Z) + [(\nabla_X A)(Z) - A(X)A(Z) + \frac{1}{2}S(X, Z)A(V)]QY \\
& - [(\nabla_Y A)(Z) - A(Y)A(Z) + \frac{1}{2}S(Y, Z)A(V)]QX \\
& + S(X, Z)[\nabla_Y V - A(Y)V + \frac{1}{2}A(V)QY] \\
& - S(Y, Z)[\nabla_X V - A(X)V + \frac{1}{2}A(V)QX].
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Now let

$$\lambda(X, Z) = (\nabla_X A)(Z) - A(X)A(Z) + \frac{1}{2}S(X, Z)A(V) = g(LX, Z), \tag{22}$$

where L is the symmetric endomorphism corresponding to the Ricci tensor with respect to the quarter symmetric metric connection D on M .

Hence (21) can be reduced to

$$\bar{R}(X, Y, Z) = R(X, Y, Z) + \lambda(X, Z)QY - \lambda(Y, Z)QX + S(X, Z)LY - S(Y, Z)LX. \tag{23}$$

Thus we can state the followings.

Theorem 1 *If an $G(SPRS)_n$ admits a quarter symmetric metric connection D , then the curvature tensor with respect to D is of the form (23).*

Corollary 1 *On a $G(SPRS)_n$ admitting a quarter symmetric metric connection D , λ defined by (22) is symmetric iff A is closed.*

Corollary 2 *On a $G(SPRS)_n$ admitting a quarter symmetric metric connection D , the necessary and sufficient condition for $\bar{R} = R$ is that*

$$\lambda(X, Z)QY - \lambda(Y, Z)QX + S(X, Z)LY - S(Y, Z)LX = 0, \tag{24}$$

where λ is defined by (22).

§4. Ricci Tensor and Scalar Curvature with Respect to a Quarter Symmetric Metric Connection on $G(SPRS)_n$

Now contracting (23) with respect to X we get,

$$\bar{S}(Y, Z) = S(Y, Z) + \lambda(QY, Z) - r\lambda(Y, Z) + \lambda(Y, QZ) - aS(Y, Z), \tag{25}$$

where

$$a = tr.L = divA + \frac{r-2}{2}A(\rho). \tag{26}$$

Again contracting (25) with respect to Y, Z and using (22) and (15) we can get,

$$\bar{r} = r + (\nabla_{QX}A)(X) + (\nabla_XA)(QX) - dr(X)A(X) + 2A(X)A(X)r. \quad (27)$$

These give us the following theorem.

Theorem 2 *If an $G(SPRS)_n$ admits a quarter symmetric metric connection D , then the Ricci tensor and scalar curvature with respect to D is of the form (25) and (27) respectively.*

§5. Examples

Let us consider M^3 be an open subsets of R^3 with the basis $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ where

$$e_1 = \frac{1}{x^1 x^3} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1}, \quad e_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2}, \quad e_3 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^3}. \quad (28)$$

Let us define the metric g as

$$g(e_i, e_j) = \begin{cases} 1, & i = j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then form of the metric is

$$g = g_{ij} dx^i dx^j = (x^1 x^3)^2 (dx^1)^2 + (dx^2)^2 + (dx^3)^2, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3. \quad (29)$$

Obviously it is a Riemannian metric. Then the Ricci tensor is

$$S_{11} = (x^1)^2, S_{11,1} = 2x^1 \quad (30)$$

and all others vanish identically, where $(,)$ denotes the covariant differentiation with respect to metric g .

Now we define

$$A_i(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{x^1}, & i = 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad B_i(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{3}{x^1}, & i = 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

for any point $x \in M$, Then

$$S_{11} = A_1 S_{11} + B_1 S_{11} \quad (31)$$

and all other forms vanish identically. The relation (31) implies that the above Riemannian manifold (M^3, g) is a $G(SPRS)_3$.

Now let the symmetric endomorphism Q defined by

$$Q(e_1) = (x^1)^2 e_1, \quad Q(e_2) = e_3, \quad Q(e_3) = e_2 \quad (32)$$

and let the vector field $V = -\frac{1}{x^1}e_1$ so that $A(X) = g(X, V)$. Then we get,

$$[e_i, e_j] = 0, \quad \forall \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3. \quad (33)$$

Then using Koszul's formula we have

$$\nabla_{e_i} e_j = 0, \quad \forall \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \quad (34)$$

where ∇ is Levi-Civita connection with respect to g .

Again using (19) we can define a connection D on M as follows:

$$D_{e_2} e_1 = -\frac{1}{x^1} e_3, D_{e_3} e_1 = -\frac{1}{x^1} e_2 \quad (35)$$

and all others vanish identically.

Using (11) we can find the torsion tensor with respect to D as follows:

$$T(e_1, e_2) = \frac{1}{x^1} e_3, T(e_1, e_3) = \frac{1}{x^1} e_2 \quad (36)$$

and all others vanish identically.

Using (12) we have

$$(D_{e_1} g)(e_2, e_3) = (D_{e_2} g)(e_1, e_3) = (D_{e_3} g)(e_2, e_1) = 0. \quad (37)$$

The above approves that D is a quarter symmetric metric connection on M . Thus (M^3, g) is a $G(SPRS)_3$ with a quarter symmetric metric connection D .

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